
Concept-Based Mechanistic Interpretability Needs a Concrete Evaluation Paradigm

Yiming Tang*

National University of Singapore

Qinglin Qi

Lund University

Zheng Lin

Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

Dianbo Liu[†]

National University of Singapore

Abstract

This position paper argues that concept-based mechanistic interpretability lacks a concrete evaluation paradigm and that the field must converge on one before continuing to scale methods whose effectiveness remains unverified. Sparse Dictionary Learning (SDL), encompassing sparse autoencoders, transcoders, crosscoders, and their variants, has become the dominant methodology for concept-based mechanistic interpretability, supported by a growing evaluation suite: reconstruction loss, automated interpretability scoring, human evaluation, feature absorption rates, sparse probing, and model editing benchmarks. Despite the significant empirical success SDL has achieved, we argue that none of these evaluation metrics directly measures what SDL is actually supposed to achieve: recovering the ground-truth features underlying observed representations. This insufficiency is structural, not incidental, and we support this perspective with both theoretical and empirical evidence. On the theoretical side, we build on the most recent formal analyses of SDL in mechanistic interpretability to show that the optimization landscape provably admits failure modes that existing metrics cannot detect. On the empirical side, we present three lines of evidence demonstrating that methods spanning a wide range of ground-truth recovery performance appear indistinguishable under current evaluation practice. Together, these results call for a new evaluation paradigm. We propose a set of principles that an ideal evaluation benchmark for concept-based mechanistic interpretability should satisfy, and argue for the community to develop and adopt more benchmarks grounded in these principles before continuing to scale methods whose effectiveness remains unverified.

1 Introduction

Understanding what concepts are encoded in the internal representations of large language models (LLMs) and vision-language models (VLMs) has become one of the central challenges of modern machine learning. As neural networks achieve remarkable capabilities across diverse domains [Vaswani et al., 2023, Radford et al., 2021], understanding *what* they represent and *how* they encode concepts is essential both for scientific progress and for the trustworthy deployment of AI systems [Bereska and Gavves, 2024, Sharkey et al., 2025]. Without such understanding, we cannot reliably predict model behavior, identify failure modes, or verify alignment with human values.

Sparse Dictionary Learning has emerged as the dominant paradigm for this program. SDL methods — including sparse autoencoders [Cunningham et al., 2023, Bricken et al., 2023, Gao et al., 2024],

*Email: yiming@nus.edu.sg

[†]Corresponding author. Email: dianbo@nus.edu.sg

transcoders [Dunefsky et al., 2024, Paulo et al., 2025], and crosscoders [Lindsey et al., 2024] — decompose polysemantic neural representations into candidate monosemantic features, scaling to frontier models [Templeton et al., 2024] and enabling downstream applications from circuit analysis [O’Neill and Bui, 2024] to medical imaging [Abdulaal et al., 2024]. The field has developed a growing suite of evaluation methods to assess these approaches: reconstruction loss and sparsity metrics, automated interpretability scoring [Paulo et al., 2024], human evaluation [Bricken et al., 2023, Tang et al., 2025a], feature absorption rates [Chanin et al., 2025], sparse probing [Kantamneni et al., 2025], and model editing benchmarks [Huang et al., 2024, Karvonen et al., 2025].

However, as theoretical frameworks emerge to rigorously analyze sparse autoencoders [Cui et al., 2025] and sparse dictionary learning [Tang et al., 2026], we observe that none of these evaluation methods directly measures the central goal of SDL: recovering the ground-truth features $\mathbf{x}(s)$ underlying the observed representations. Task performance metrics measure downstream utility, not representational fidelity. Interpretation alignment metrics are bounded by the expressivity of natural language as a medium for describing representational structure. Feature absorption scores provide an indirect measure on recovery failures over a pre-specified concept vocabulary. And ground-truth recovery evaluation, the only metric that directly measures what SDL is supposed to achieve, is currently feasible only in synthetic settings [Tang et al., 2026]. The field has converged on a suite of evaluation proxies without resolving whether any of them reliably indicates genuine feature recovery.

We support our claim that concept-based mechanistic interpretability needs a concrete evaluation paradigm with both theoretical and empirical evidence. On the theoretical side, three results establish the structural insufficiency of existing metrics. First, SDL optimization is provably underdetermined: the solution space admits configurations that achieve zero reconstruction loss while recovering no ground-truth features [Tang et al., 2026], meaning reconstruction loss cannot distinguish success from failure. Second, even the optimal solution under realistic sparsity provably distorts features through shrinking and vanishing [Cui et al., 2025], introducing irreducible error invisible to reconstruction-based evaluation. Third, spurious partial minima exhibiting polysemanticity are pervasive by construction, and polysemantic features are seemingly interpretable — meaning current evaluation metrics cannot distinguish them from genuine monosemantic recovery.

On the empirical side, we present three lines of evidence. First, on synthetic datasets [Tang et al., 2026], SDL methods spanning 0% to 89% GT Recovery appear indistinguishable under reconstruction metrics, directly demonstrating that reconstruction loss cannot detect recovery failure. Second, qualitative analysis of fMRI and CLIP embedding interpretations reveals features corresponding to low-level visual patterns that are faithfully recovered yet resist concise natural language description, exposing a systematic blind spot in interpretation alignment metrics, which conflate linguistic expressibility with representational fidelity. Third, analysis of CLIP embeddings reveals features that are genuinely polysemantic yet receive high interpretability scores, because human language can express non-monosemantic concepts coherently; this shows that automated interpretability scoring cannot distinguish genuine monosemantic recovery from spurious polysemantic solutions.

Together, these theoretical and empirical results demonstrate that the insufficiency of existing evaluation metrics is not incidental but structural. We argue for a concrete benchmark for concept-based mechanistic interpretability and propose four principles this benchmark should have based on our analysis and evidence. We aim to catalyze community-wide convergence on evaluation standards before the field continues to scale methods whose effectiveness remains unverified. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 surveys SDL methods and their role in concept-based mechanistic interpretability. Section 3 organizes existing evaluation approaches into seven families and reviews the state of the art in each. Section 4 analyses the structural limitations of each evaluation family and explains why none directly measures ground-truth feature recovery. Section 5 presents the theoretical evidence, drawing on recent formal analyses of the SDL optimization landscape to establish three provable failure modes. Section 6 presents three empirical demonstrations that these failure modes manifest under standard training and evaluation practice. Section 7 proposes four principles for a concrete evaluation paradigm and outlines a minimum benchmark specification. Section 8 addresses four viable counterpositions to our argument. Section 9 concludes.

2 SDL Methods and Concept-Based Mechanistic Interpretability

A central question in mechanistic interpretability is identifying what concepts are encoded in the internal representations of neural networks [Bereska and Gavves, 2024, Sharkey et al., 2025]. This question is important both scientifically, as a step toward reverse-engineering how models process information, and practically, for the safe deployment of AI systems where understanding internal representations is a prerequisite for verifying model behavior. Researchers have widely utilized the linear representation hypothesis: models encode meaningful concepts as linear directions in activation space, often in superposition where individual neurons respond to multiple unrelated concepts [Elhage et al., 2022, Park et al., 2024, Marks and Tegmark, 2024, Park et al., 2025].

Sparse Dictionary Learning has emerged as the dominant paradigm for concept-based mechanistic interpretability at scale, owing to its ability to decompose polysemantic activations into candidate monosemantic features [Shu et al., 2025]. Sparse autoencoders reconstruct a layer’s activations through a sparse bottleneck, encouraging each latent to correspond to a single interpretable concept [Cunningham et al., 2023, Bricken et al., 2023]. Architectural variants targeting sparsity quality include JumpReLU [Rajamanoharan et al., 2024b], Gated [Rajamanoharan et al., 2024a], TopK [Gao et al., 2024], BatchTopK [Busmann et al., 2024], and Matryoshka SAEs [Busmann et al., 2025]. Transcoders extend the SDL framework beyond self-reconstruction, learning sparse approximations of layer-to-layer transformations [Dunefsky et al., 2024, Paulo et al., 2025], while crosscoders jointly encode and reconstruct activations across multiple layers or models [Lindsey et al., 2024]. These methods have been scaled to frontier language models [Templeton et al., 2024] and extended to vision and multimodal representations [Tang et al., 2025b,d], protein language models [Simon and Zou, 2024, Gujral et al., 2025], and medical imaging [Abdulaal et al., 2024, Tang et al., 2025f]. Recently, theoretical frameworks have been proposed to analyze SDL methods used in mechanistic interpretability [Cui et al., 2025, Tang et al., 2025c], and a key observation emerging from this line of work is that the field has not converged on a rigorous standard for evaluating whether these methods achieve their central goal, recovering the ground-truth concepts encoded in model representations.

Beyond concept identification, SDL features have been applied to a growing range of downstream tasks. Feature steering uses identified directions to causally intervene on model behavior [Wang et al., 2025], and circuit analysis uses SDL decompositions to identify the computational subgraphs responsible for specific model behaviors [O’Neill and Bui, 2024]. SDL features have also been applied to model editing and knowledge unlearning [Farrell et al., 2024], disentanglement of factual attributes [Huang et al., 2024], prompt discovery [Saini et al., 2026b], and failure mode analysis [Tang et al., 2025e]. This breadth of application has made SDL methods the central infrastructure of modern mechanistic interpretability, and raises the stakes of the evaluation question we address in this paper.

3 How Are SDL Methods Evaluated Today?

SDL methods are assessed through a growing but fragmented set of metrics. We organize these into seven families based on what each fundamentally measures.

3.1 Reconstruction and Sparsity Metrics

Reconstruction loss and sparsity (L_0) are the canonical metrics [Cunningham et al., 2023, Bricken et al., 2023, Gao et al., 2024, Templeton et al., 2024]: the former measures how well the decoder recovers the original activation; the latter counts active features per input. The loss-recovered ratio [Karvonen et al., 2025] measures how much downstream model loss is preserved when activations are replaced with SAE reconstructions. Further variants include quasi-orthogonality criteria for hyperparameter selection [Lee et al., 2025], matching-pursuit baselines [Costa et al., 2025], and polysemous word sense disambiguation as a monosemanticity proxy [Minegishi et al., 2025].

3.2 Human & LMM Evaluation

Large language models or human annotators rate whether maximally activating examples exhibit a coherent concept [Cunningham et al., 2023, Bricken et al., 2023, Luo et al., 2023, Tang and Dong, 2024, ?]; human-agreement evaluation [Tang et al., 2025a] calibrates this via inter-annotator agreement. LMM evaluation scales this approach: an LLM generates a natural-language label

from top-activating examples and predicts held-out activations, with prediction accuracy as the score [Templeton et al., 2024, Gao et al., 2024, Paulo et al., 2024]. Extensions include output-centric descriptions [Gur-Arieh et al., 2025], multimodal agentic interpretation [Shaham et al., 2025], and crowdsourced calibration [Oikarinen et al., 2025]. The validity of these scores has been questioned: they are sensitive to prompt design [Lermen and Kvapil, 2023], fail to distinguish trained from random transformers [Heap et al., 2026], and are susceptible to adversarial manipulation [Lermen et al., 2025].

3.3 Sparse Probing

Sparse probing trains a linear classifier on a small subset of SAE latents to predict concept labels, comparing accuracy against probing on raw activations [Gao et al., 2024, Gurnee et al., 2023]. Kantamneni et al. [2025] find mixed results depending on concept type and layer; SAEBench [Karvonen et al., 2025] includes it as a core evaluation component.

3.4 Feature Absorption Rate

Feature absorption [Chanin et al., 2025] occurs when a broad SDL feature subsumes a sub-concept (e.g. *the letter “a” in general* absorbs *lowercase “a”*), leaving the sub-concept unrecoverable. The measurement protocol checks whether any single SDL feature reliably activates on concept-positive inputs generated by an LLM; SAEBench includes this as the *Absorption* evaluation [Karvonen et al., 2025]. Orthogonality constraints have been proposed to mitigate absorption [Korzniakov et al., 2025].

3.5 Performance on Downstream Tasks

Downstream evaluations test whether features support targeted interventions. RAVEL [Huang et al., 2024] and SCR/TPP [Karvonen et al., 2024a] measure causal disentanglement and probing-accuracy changes under feature activation or suppression; unlearning evaluations [Farrell et al., 2024] test selective knowledge removal; feature steering assesses interpretable behavioral control [Wang et al., 2025, Saini et al., 2026a]. Robustness evaluation [Li et al., 2026] finds many features brittle under adversarial perturbation despite high interpretability scores, showing these properties are orthogonal.

3.6 Ground-Truth Feature Recovery

Ground-truth feature recovery is the only family that directly measures alignment with the underlying representational structure. Board-game models provide semi-naturalistic ground truth [Karvonen et al., 2024b]; the Linear Representation Bench [Tang et al., 2026] provides a fully synthetic alternative with known W_p^{true} , enabling direct computation of M_{GT} and M_{IP} . SAGE [Venhoff et al., 2024] and SynthSAEBench [Chanin and Garriga-Alonso, 2026] scale this toward naturalistic settings; Fereidouni et al. [2025] benchmark SAEs on monosemantic neuron recovery as a primary criterion.

3.7 Unified Benchmark Suites

SAEBench [Karvonen et al., 2025] is the current field standard, consolidating reconstruction, sparse probing, RAVEL, SCR/TPP, feature absorption, and automated interpretability into a single framework. MIB [Mueller et al., 2025] extends coverage to circuit analysis and causal tracing across five models. CE-Bench [Gulko et al., 2025] introduces concept-contrastive evaluation with known ground truth; Song et al. [2025] argue for feature consistency across training runs as a quality signal.

4 Limitations of Existing Evaluation Methods

Despite the diversity of evaluation approaches surveyed above, none directly and reliably measures whether SDL methods have faithfully recovered the model’s representational structure. Each family conflates the recovery goal with a proxy that can come apart from it in systematic ways.

Reconstruction and sparsity metrics are structurally disconnected from the recovery goal. Reconstruction loss measures activation fidelity, not latent alignment: zero loss is achievable by infinitely many solutions, most recovering no ground-truth features (Theorem 5.1). The optimal solution under realistic sparsity still provably distorts features through shrinking and vanishing [Cui et al., 2025].

Human & LMM evaluation fails in two complementary directions. Polysemantic features receive high scores when their dominant activations form a linguistically coherent cluster, regardless of whether any ground-truth concept is recovered. Faithfully recovered features are undercounted when the underlying concept resists concise natural language description (Section 6). Scores are also prompt-sensitive [Lermen and Kvapil, 2023, Heap et al., 2026], and are adversarially manipulable [Lermen et al., 2025].

Sparse probing is a utility metric, not a fidelity metric. Polysemantic features can match raw activations on probing accuracy by encoding concept-relevant signal in combinations, with no correspondence to the model’s atomic representational structure. Probing also evaluates only features that activate on a pre-specified concept vocabulary, leaving most of the dictionary untested.

Feature absorption rate measures one specific failure mode but provides only a lower bound on recovery failures. The protocol requires a pre-specified concept vocabulary [Chanin et al., 2025]; absorption of out-of-vocabulary concepts goes unmeasured. In vision and multimodal settings, generating concept-contrastive datasets requires non-trivial infrastructure, making the metric impractical at the scale where it would be most informative.

Downstream task performance conflates utility with fidelity. Polysemantic features can support effective steering or disentanglement while misrepresenting the model’s representational structure; faithful features may be irrelevant to any given task. Karvonen et al. [2025] reports this directly: reconstruction gains do not translate reliably to other evaluation categories, and metric choice determines which architectures appear best, with no principled basis for preferring tasks.

Ground-truth feature recovery is the only family whose limitations are practical rather than conceptual. The LRB and board-game benchmarks require ground truth available by construction [Tang et al., 2026, Karvonen et al., 2024b]. SAGE [Venhoff et al., 2024] and SynthSAEBench [Chanin and Garriga-Alonso, 2026] partially bridge this gap, but scalable ground-truth proxies for frontier LLM representations remain an open problem [Sharkey et al., 2025].

Unified benchmark suites inherit the limitations of their component metrics. Aggregating seven insufficient proxies does not produce a sufficient evaluation. CE-Bench [Gulko et al., 2025] moves toward falsifiability but remains vocabulary-dependent; feature consistency [Song et al., 2025] is necessary for reproducibility but not sufficient for recovery.

5 Theoretical Evidences

We present existing theoretical results drawn from recent developments on sparse dictionary learning, Tang et al. [2026] and Cui et al. [2025], to support our position with rigorous mathematics.

5.1 A Theoretical Framework for SDL and Its Central Goal

Setup. Under the Linear Representation Hypothesis [Park et al., 2024, Elhage et al., 2022], a model’s internal representation at a given layer can be decomposed as

$$\mathbf{x}_p(s) = W_p \mathbf{x}(s), \quad \mathbf{x}_r(s) = W_r \mathbf{x}(s), \quad (1)$$

where s indexes inputs drawn from a data distribution \mathcal{D} , $\mathbf{x}(s) \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ is a sparse vector of n ground-truth features encoding interpretable concepts, and $W_p \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p \times n}$, $W_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n}$ are fixed projection matrices mapping ground-truth features into the observed probe and reconstruction spaces respectively. The ground-truth features $\mathbf{x}(s)$ are never observed during training; only the projected representations $\mathbf{x}_p(s)$ and $\mathbf{x}_r(s)$ are accessible.

The SDL objective. SDL methods train an auxiliary encoder-decoder pair (W_E, W_D) with $W_E \in \mathbb{R}^{n_q \times n_p}$ and $W_D \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_q}$ to minimize the reconstruction objective

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SDL}}(W_D, W_E) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \mathcal{D}} [\|\mathbf{x}_r(s) - W_D \sigma(W_E \mathbf{x}_p(s))\|_2^2], \quad (2)$$

where n_q is the number of learned features (dictionary size) and σ is a sparsity-inducing activation function. This formulation encompasses the major SDL architectures as special cases [Tang et al., 2026]: sparse autoencoders set $\mathbf{x}_p = \mathbf{x}_r$ (probing and reconstructing the same activation), transcoders set \mathbf{x}_p and \mathbf{x}_r to successive layer activations to model layer-to-layer transformations, and crosscoders generalize this to joint encoding and reconstruction across multiple layers or models. In all cases the

encoder W_E maps observed representations into a learned latent space of candidate features, and the decoder W_D maps those features back to the reconstruction target.

The central goal and the evaluation gap. The central goal of SDL in mechanistic interpretability is not to minimize \mathcal{L}_{SDL} — it is to recover the ground-truth features $\mathbf{x}(s)$ from the observed representations $\mathbf{x}_p(s)$ and $\mathbf{x}_r(s)$. These two objectives are related but not equivalent: \mathcal{L}_{SDL} is minimized over the observed quantities, while feature recovery is a property of the latent $\mathbf{x}(s)$ that is never directly observed during training. This gap between the optimization objective and the recovery goal is the root cause of the evaluation problem we identify. Genuinely assessing SDL methods requires access to $\mathbf{x}(s)$, which is unavailable in all naturalistic evaluation settings, and it is precisely this inaccessibility that allows the structural failure modes formalized in the following subsections to go undetected under current evaluation practice.

5.2 Zero Loss Does Not Imply Feature Recovery

Under the high-sparsity limit, the SDL objective \mathcal{L}_{SDL} simplifies to an approximate loss over individual ground-truth feature directions,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\text{SDL}}(W_D, W_E) = \sum_{d=1}^n \|w_r^d - W_D \sigma(W_E w_p^d)\|_2^2, \quad (3)$$

where w_p^d and w_r^d denote the d -th columns of W_p and W_r respectively [Tang et al., 2026]. Analyzing this approximate loss gives us the following conditions on the sparse dictionary learning landscape.

Theorem 5.1 (Underdetermined Solution Space, Tang et al. 2026). *Under the Linear Representation Hypothesis, $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\text{SDL}}(W_D, W_E) = O((1 - S)^2)$ if and only if $w_r^d = W_D \sigma(W_E w_p^d)$ for all $d \in [n]$. When $n_q > n$, this system is underdetermined, admitting infinitely many solutions.*

Some solutions achieve zero loss while recovering no ground-truth feature directions. A constructive near-zero-loss solution that does recover ground-truth features exists [Tang et al., 2026], but it is one among infinitely many. Complementarily, Cui et al. [2025] show that even the optimal SAE solution provably distorts features through shrinking and vanishing unless ground-truth features are extremely sparse ($S \rightarrow 1$). In both the overcomplete and undercomplete regimes, reconstruction loss cannot distinguish successful feature recovery from failure.

5.3 Polysemantic Solutions are Structurally Pervasive and Seemingly Interpretable

Beyond underdetermination, the $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\text{SDL}}$ landscape is populated with partial minima that exhibit polysemanticity by construction — and hierarchical concept structure, present in virtually all real-world representations, guarantees their existence through a provable feature absorption mechanism.

Theorem 5.2 (Prevalence of Spurious Partial Minima, Tang et al. 2026). *Under the Linear Representation Hypothesis with $n \geq 2$ and $n_q \geq n$, for any activation pattern that is realizable, polysemantic, and forms a partition of $[n]$, there is a spurious partial minimum of $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\text{SDL}}$ exhibiting this pattern.*

Theorem 5.3 (Feature Absorption from Hierarchical Structure, Tang et al. 2026). *If ground-truth features contain a parent concept decomposing into sub-concepts $\{d_{i,1}, \dots, d_{i,k_i}\}$ with $k_i \geq 2$, and the corresponding activation pattern, $\mathcal{P} = (\mathcal{F}_1, \dots, \mathcal{F}_{i^*}, \dots, \mathcal{F}_N)$, is realizable, then there exists sub-concept d_{i^*,j^*} , the absorption pattern $\mathcal{P}' = (\dots, \mathcal{F}_{i^*} \setminus \{d_{i^*,j^*}\}, \{d_{i^*,j^*}\}, \dots)$ is realizable and corresponds to a spurious partial minimum.*

Together, these results establish that polysemantic solutions are structural properties of the SDL landscape, not incidental training failures. Their presence is compounded by an evaluation blind spot: polysemantic features that activate on semantically coherent sub-concept clusters receive high interpretability scores and positive human ratings, making them indistinguishable from genuine monosemantic recovery without ground-truth access.

6 Empirical Evidence

We argue that reconstruction loss is structurally insufficient to verify feature recovery, that some correctly identified features can be hard to describe in natural language, and that polysemantic solutions are pervasive and might be seemingly interpretable. Here we present the empirical evidences.

6.1 Reconstruction Metrics Cannot Distinguish Recovery Success from Failure

Following Tang et al. [2026], we construct a fully synthetic benchmark satisfying the Linear Representation Hypothesis exactly, with known ground-truth directions W_p . Figure 1 illustrates the core failure mode: despite the ground-truth features forming a clean orthogonal basis, the learned encoder W_E and decoder W_D directions are substantially misaligned with them — yet the SDL objective converges normally. This directly instantiates Theorem 5.1: low reconstruction loss is compatible with complete recovery failure, and the two are indistinguishable under reconstruction-based evaluation.

Figure 1: **Misalignment between ground-truth and recovered feature directions.** Ground-truth features W_p^{true} form an orthogonal basis (left), yet the learned encoder W_E (centre) and decoder W_D (right) fail to recover them after SDL training — a failure entirely invisible to reconstruction loss.

6.2 Faithfully Recovered Features May Resist Natural Language Description

Interpretation alignment metrics deem a feature interpretable if a natural language label predicts its held-out activations — a criterion that conflates linguistic expressibility with representational fidelity. A common practice in mechanistic interpretability is to use LMMs to inspect high-activating samples and describe features in natural language [Paulo et al., 2024, Templeton et al., 2024]. However, human vocabulary may be insufficiently developed to ground cross-modal and low-level visual patterns accurately, creating a systematic blind spot. Moreover, features unexpected by the prompt designer may be ignored or poorly characterized by the LMM, regardless of how faithfully they are recovered.

Figure 2: **Cross-modal SDL features that resist natural language grounding.** LMM-generated descriptions for high-activating samples from natural image, fundus, chest X-ray, and fMRI encoders. Features encode coherent structure across all modalities, yet descriptions range from domain-specific (“retinal blood vessels and optic nerve head”) to vague (“complicated edge signals”) — illustrating that linguistic inexpressibility reflects the limits of language, not failures of recovery.

We train SDL modules across natural images, fundus images, chest X-rays, and fMRI representations, and apply LMMs to inspect the highest-activating samples per feature. As shown in Figure 2 and Appendix, features across modalities encode coherent, reproducible structure — retinal vasculature, pulmonary consolidation patterns, complex edge signals — yet accurate natural language

grounding remains difficult: descriptions either require narrow clinical vocabulary inaccessible to general pipelines, or collapse into vague characterizations such as “*complicated edge signals*” [Tang et al., 2025a]. Evaluation paradigms relying primarily on linguistic coherence will systematically undercount faithfully recovered features of this class.

6.3 Polysemantic Features Receive High Interpretability Scores

Polysemantic features represent the opposite failure mode: incorrectly rated as interpretable because LMM-generated descriptions adapt to mask underlying ambiguity. We construct a controlled experiment using ImageNet-1K class mean embeddings as ground-truth feature proxies. As shown in Figure 3, Feature 1 (dish racks, 95%) and Feature 2 (recreational vehicles, 96%) individually receive precise, high-confidence LMM evaluations. Summing the two embeddings and raising the activation threshold produces a feature that is polysemantic by construction — yet it still scores 92%. Rather than flagging a conflict, the LMM retreats to a coarser superordinate label: “*household furniture and interior design items*” — technically defensible yet losing the specificity of both concepts entirely.

The consequence is a coverage blind spot: a run absorbing ground-truth concepts into spurious polysemantic combinations will report high interpretability scores with no signal of what is missing. Ground-truth recovery metrics measure coverage; automated scoring does not.

Figure 3: **Polysemantic features receive high automated interpretability scores.** Feature 1 (dish racks, 95%) and Feature 2 (recreational vehicles, 96%) each receive precise labels. Their sum — polysemantic by construction — scores 92%, but the LMM description retreats to the coarse superordinate “*household furniture and interior design items,*” masking the loss of specificity rather than flagging a conflict.

7 Toward a Concrete Evaluation Paradigm

The preceding analysis converges on a conclusion: the field needs an evaluation paradigm anchored in ground-truth feature recovery, encompassing frontier models. Based on our theoretical and empirical evidence, we propose four principles as a concrete standard.

- **Ground-Truth Accessibility.** Benchmarks must provide known representational structure, via a tiered approach: synthetic benchmarks with exact ground truth (e.g. LRB [Tang et al., 2026]) for controlled comparison; semi-synthetic settings as a bridge; and naturalistic settings using human-agreement evaluation [Tang et al., 2025a] as a fidelity proxy. Developing

scalable ground-truth proxies for frontier models remains the field’s most important open problem [Sharkey et al., 2025].

- **Falsifiability.** Evaluation must be capable of reporting failure, not merely degrees of success. GT Recovery satisfies this — 0% M_{GT} is an unambiguous failure signal — whereas reconstruction loss does not (Theorem 5.1). Every SDL evaluation should report at minimum: (i) GT Recovery on a synthetic benchmark; (ii) dead neuron and absorption rates as primary outcomes; and (iii) reconstruction loss and sparsity as secondary context.
- **Coverage Beyond Linear Features.** Features encoding periodic structure are irreducibly multi-dimensional [Engels et al., 2025] and unrecoverable by standard SAEs. A rigorous benchmark must include features with known non-linear geometry and extend to vision and multimodal representations [Tang et al., 2025a,e], where cross-modal alignment introduces challenges unimodal SDL frameworks are not designed to address.
- **Separating Utility from Fidelity.** Utility (whether features support a downstream task) and fidelity (whether they reflect the model’s representational structure) are distinct properties the field currently conflates [Lipton, 2017]. Evaluation protocols must explicitly separate utility metrics (task performance) from fidelity metrics (GT Recovery, absorption rate).

8 Alternative Views

We identify three viable counterpositions and address each in turn.

8.1 “Human&LMM Evaluation Fills the Gap”

Linguistic coherence is a meaningful property, and we do not object to human or LMM evaluation as a component of the evaluation suite. Our objection is to its sufficiency. It cannot detect two structural failure modes: polysemantic features activating on semantically coherent but spurious clusters score well while recovering no ground-truth concept; and human or LMM evaluation assesses only the features SDL does recover, remaining silent about those it fails to recover.

8.2 “The Field Is Young; Evaluation Will Mature Naturally”

Progress has been genuine — feature absorption [Chanin et al., 2025] and ground-truth benchmarks [Karvonen et al., 2024b, Tang et al., 2026] are real advances. Our concern is the cost of unguided maturation. Inception score, BLEU, and probing accuracy all required substantial reinterpretation of accumulated work once their insufficiency was recognized. Mechanistic interpretability, whose conclusions bear directly on AI safety [Bereska and Gavves, 2024, Sharkey et al., 2025], faces particularly high costs if its progress metrics prove insufficient. The argument for explicit standards is strongest precisely when the stakes are highest.

8.3 “Ground-Truth Features Do Not Exist in Real Models”

The constructivist objection holds that SDL methods build useful decompositions rather than recover pre-existing features, making reconstruction fidelity an appropriate measure of construction quality. Two responses suffice. First, synthetic settings with known ground truth provide a necessary condition regardless of how the philosophical question resolves: a method failing to recover accessible ground-truth features has demonstrated a concrete limitation. Second, the constructivist view strengthens our argument for separating utility from fidelity: if features are constructions, reconstruction loss measures compression quality, not interpretability quality — making explicit interpretability metrics more necessary, not less. Either way, current evaluation is insufficient.

9 Conclusion

Concept-based mechanistic interpretability cannot verify its own progress without an evaluation paradigm grounded in four commitments: ground-truth accessibility, falsifiability, coverage beyond linear features, and explicit separation of utility from fidelity. The theoretical and empirical evidence presented here shows that the current suite of proxies is structurally incapable of detecting the failure modes that matter most. We call on the community to adopt these principles before continuing to

scale methods whose effectiveness remains unverified — particularly given that the program’s stated motivation is AI safety, where the cost of undetected failure is highest.

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